
PERSONAL EXPOSURE AND HEALTH DATA PLATFORM PROCESSOR AGREEMENT

Version: v1.0

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Pursuant to the Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and the Commission Decision 2010/87/EU on standard contractual clauses for the transfer of personal data.

by and between

..... (Org. no, address)

Email address DPO:

Hereafter referred to as the "Controller"

and

VITO

a limited liability company, incorporated under the laws of Belgium (Register of Legal Entities Turnhout 0244.195.916), with its registered office at Boeretang 200, 2400 Mol, Belgium

contact details DPO: assist-DPO@vito.be

Hereafter referred to as the "Processor"

Hereinafter individually referred to as a "Party" and collectively as the "Parties".

Preliminary provisions

The intention of this processor agreement (hereinafter the "Agreement") is to regulate the processing of the personal data that the Processor handles on behalf of the Controller pursuant to the Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data ('GDPR').

The Agreement shall ensure that personal data relating to the data subjects is not used unlawfully or comes into the hands of a third party.

The Agreement regulates the Processor's processing of personal data on behalf of the Controller.

The Agreement stipulates the rights and obligations of both the Controller and the Processor.

Article 1: Subject-matter of the Agreement

The Processor shall process personal data on behalf of the Controller in the context of the services provided through the Personal Exposure and Health (PEH) Data Platform.

The details concerning processing activities performed by the Processor on behalf of the Controller are specified in **appendix 1**, which forms an integral part of this Agreement. Such details are:

- categories of personal data;
- categories of data subjects;
- purposes of the processing; and
- processing activities.

Only personal data which is mentioned in **appendix 1** may and shall be processed by the Processor. Furthermore, personal data shall only be processed in light of the purposes which are included in **appendix 1** by the Parties.

The processing activities are limited to the services provided by the PEH Data Platform, including the processing of single measurement data for validation, harmonization, enrichment, and the generation of derived outputs. In the context of this agreement, single measurement data are records of a data collection obtained from single data subjects, obtained at personal level including data on human biomonitoring (HBM), effect markers, health markers, personal environmental exposure, exposure determinants, and other accompanying variables.

For the avoidance of doubt, this Agreement governs the processing of personal data by the Processor, including both single measurement data and contact details of the data provider. Such processing does not include making single measurement data accessible to third parties or stakeholders, except where required by law. The use, sharing, or publication of summary statistics, metadata, and other outputs is governed by the PEH Data Platform Terms and Conditions.

Further instructions of the Controller are defined in Appendix 2 and in the PEH Data Platform Terms and Conditions (available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20639231>).

Article 2: Duration of the processing

This Agreement shall apply as long as the Processor processes personal data on behalf of the Controller in the framework of the service agreement referred to in the preliminary provisions of this Agreement.

The Processor shall not retain single measurement data for longer than necessary to fulfil the purposes of the processing as defined in this Agreement.

Retention periods may depend on the duration of the services provided through the PEH Data Platform and the operational needs related to data validation, harmonization, enrichment, and calculation of summary statistics.

Article 3: Applicable legislation

Both Parties explicitly commit to comply with the requirements of the GDPR.

Article 4: The Controller's Instructions

The Processor processes the personal data only on the documented instructions of the Controller set out in **appendix 2** and shall not further process the personal data subject to this Agreement in a manner which is incompatible with these instructions and the provisions laid down in this Agreement.

The Processor processes the personal data only on documented instructions from the Controller, including with regard to transfers of personal data to a third country or an international organization, unless required to do so by Union or Member State law to which the Processor is subject; in such a case, the Processor shall inform the Controller of that legal requirement before processing, unless that law prohibits such information on important grounds of public interest.

The Processor shall be consulted before any changes are made to the instructions. The Controller can make limited changes to the instructions unilaterally, but changes affecting the core of the Agreement must be agreed upon by both Parties.

The Processor shall immediately inform the Controller if, in its opinion, an instruction infringes the GDPR or other Union or Member State data protection provisions to which the Processor is subject.

The Controller's instructions include the processing activities as described in Appendix 1 and are further detailed in the PEH Data Platform Terms and Conditions that are to be accepted prior to uploading any data. PEH Data Platform Terms and Conditions are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20639231>.

Article 5: The use of sub-processors

The Controller authorizes the Processor to engage sub-processors, the Processor shall inform the Controller of any intended changes concerning the addition or replacement of sub-processors.

In case the Processor engages a sub-processor for carrying out specific processing activities on behalf of the Controller, the same data protection obligations as set out in this Agreement shall be imposed on that other sub-processor by way of a contract, in particular providing sufficient guarantees to implement appropriate technical and organizational measures in such a manner that the processing will meet the requirements of the GDPR.

Where that other sub-processor fails to fulfil its data protection obligations, the initial Processor shall remain fully liable to the Controller for the performance of that sub-processor's obligations.

Article 6: Confidentiality

The Processor commits himself to handle the personal data and its processing with utter confidentiality.

The Processor ensures that persons authorized to process the personal data have committed themselves to confidentiality or are under an appropriate statutory obligation of confidentiality.

Article 7: Security measures

The Processor shall implement appropriate technical and organizational measures in such a manner that processing will meet the requirements of the GDPR and ensure the protection of the rights of the data subject.

The Processor shall implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to the risk, according to article 32 of the GDPR.

In assessing the appropriate level of security account was taken in particular of the risks that are presented by processing, in particular from accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure of, or access to personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed.

Where the Processor changes the applicable security measures, he shall immediately inform the Controller of such changes.

A general description of the technical and organization security measures is included in **appendix 3** to this Agreement.

Article 8: Rights of the data subjects

Taking into account the nature of the processing, the Processor assists the Controller by appropriate technical and organizational measures, insofar as this is possible, for the fulfillment of the Controller's obligation to respond to requests for exercising the data subject's rights laid down in Chapter III of the GDPR.

Article 9: Assistance to the Controller

The Processor shall assist the Controller in ensuring compliance with its obligations pursuant to the GDPR, taking into account the nature of processing and the information available of the Processor.

In the case of a personal data breach related to the processing subject of this Agreement, the Processor shall notify the Controller when becoming aware of a personal data breach.

This notification shall at least include following information:

- a) the nature of the personal data breach;
- b) the categories of personal data;
- c) the categories and approximate number of data subjects concerned; and
- d) the categories and approximate number of personal data records concerned.

Furthermore the Processor shall assist the Controller in the assessment of the consequences of the personal data breach and the measures taken or proposed to be taken to address the personal data breach, including, where appropriate, measures to mitigate its possible adverse effects.

The Processor shall assist the Controller as he carries out a data protection impact assessment (DPIA) in accordance with article 35 of the GDPR.

Article 10: Transfer to Third Parties

The Processor may share contact details with third parties only where strictly necessary for verification, clarification, or communication purposes related to the data, in accordance with Appendix 1 and the PEH Data Platform Terms and Conditions.

The transfer of any other personal data (such as single measurement data) to third parties, in any manner possible is prohibited, unless it's legally required or in case the Processor has obtained the explicit consent by the Controller to do so. In case a legal obligation to transfer single measurement data, which are subject to this Agreement, to third parties, applies, the Processor shall prior to the transfer notify the Controller.

The sharing of aggregated data, metadata, and other outputs is governed by the PEH Data Platform Terms and Conditions.

Article 11: Audit by the Controller

The Controller is entitled to evaluate the compliance with this processor agreement. He has the right to conduct an audit at any time on the location where the processing activities take place, after scheduling appointments with the Processor.

The Processor makes available to the Controller all information necessary to demonstrate compliance with the obligations laid down in article 28 of the GDPR allow for and contribute to audits, including inspections, conducted by the Controller or another auditor mandated by the Controller, at the charge of the Controller.

Article 12: Liability

The Controller is responsible for obtaining the consent of the data subject for processing his or her personal data according to the provisions of the GDPR.

The Processor is liable for the damage caused by processing only where it has not complied with obligations of the GDPR specifically directed to processors where it has acted outside or contrary to lawful instructions of the Controller.

The Processor is liable to pay administrative fines which derive from its breach of the provisions of the GDPR.

The Processor shall be exempt from his liability, if he proves that he's not responsible for the event giving rise to the damage.

Each Party undertakes not to bring any extracontractual claims in connection with this Agreement against the other Party, nor against the directors, employees or agents of the Party, except in cases of wilful misconduct or where such an exclusion is prohibited by law.

This undertaking does not prejudice any rights which a Party might have to make a contractual claim or bring contractual proceedings against the other Party.

Article 13: Intellectual Property Rights

All intellectual property rights as regards to the personal data and as regards to the databases which contain these personal data are reserved to the Controller, unless otherwise contractually agreed upon between the Parties.

Article 14: Termination of the contract

In the event of breach of this Agreement or the GDPR, the Controller can instruct the Processor to stop further processing of the personal data with immediate effect.

This Agreement can be terminated by both Parties with a mutual period of notice of 30 days.

The Processor shall not store the personal data any longer than needed to perform the service for which the personal data is provided. At the choice of the Controller, the Processor shall delete or return all the personal data to the Controller after the end of the provision of services relation to processing, and deletes existing copies unless Union or Member State law requires storage of the personal data. The personal data shall be provided to the Controller in a defined conventional format without additional charge, unless otherwise agreed upon. If the Controller did not announce his choice at the time the agreement ends, the Processor will delete all personal data by default.

Upon termination of the Agreement, single measurement data shall be deleted or returned to the Controller without undue delay, unless retention is required by Union or Member State law.

Where applicable, aggregated data and metadata may be retained, provided that such data no longer allow the identification of individual data subjects.

Article 15: Exhaustiveness of the Agreement

In the event that either one of these contractual clauses is destroyed or elucidated non-valid in any other way, the rest of the contract still applies and the concerning contractual clause shall be replaced by a valid contractual clause which correctly represents the initial intentions of the Parties.

Article 16: Electronic signature

Parties agree that the execution of the Agreement by industry standard electronic signature software and/or by exchanging PDF signatures shall have the same legal force and effect as the exchange of original signatures, and that in any proceedings arising under or relating to the Agreement, Parties waives any right to raise any defence or waiver based upon execution of the Agreement by means of such electronic signatures or maintenance of the executed agreement electronically.

Done at [place] on [date].

On behalf of the Controller

On behalf of the Processor

Name: [..]

Name: [..]

Function: [..]

Function: [..]

Appendix 1: Processing Personal Data

List of personal data being processed:

- Single measurement Personal Exposure and Health data that are uploaded to the PEH Data Platform:
 - In accordance with the instructions of the Processor, the Controller provides that data in the required format (following codebooks and data templates)
 - The Controller shall only provide pseudonymized data and/or fully anonymized data to the PEH Data Platform
- Contact details of the data provider and any other contact details that are provided as contact point concerning the uploaded data (excluding contact details of study data subjects)

Categories of data subjects:

- Participants of population studies. Those may be, but are not limited to:
 - Children
 - Minors
 - Adults
 - Volunteers
 - Patients
 - Workers

Purposes of the processing and legitimate base¹:

- Data harmonization according to PEH Data Platform standards;
- Data validation and quality control of uploaded datasets;
- Data enrichment (generation of derived variables);
- Derivation of aggregated outputs and related information from the single measurement data;
- No purpose includes making single measurement data accessible to third parties or stakeholders;
- The Processor shall not use the personal data for its own purposes, including research, development, or analytics, unless explicitly agreed with the Controller
- Retention of personal data is limited to what is necessary for the purposes of the processing, taking into account the different categories of data:
 - Single measurement data shall be retained only for the period necessary to perform data validation, harmonization, enrichment, and aggregation activities, after which they shall be deleted or anonymized where possible.
 - Contact details of the data provider may be retained for a longer period, as necessary to:
 - verify and clarify data-related questions;
 - ensure traceability of the dataset;
 - enable follow-up communication regarding the study and its outputs;
 - comply with applicable legal obligations.

The Processor shall ensure that retention periods are reviewed periodically and that personal data is not kept longer than necessary. **Processing activities:**

- Upload and ingestion of datasets;
- Data harmonization pipelines;
- Automated and manual validation processes;
- Generation of aggregated outputs and derived information

¹ List of services as in the service agreement

- Secure storage and processing within the Processor's PEH Data Platform infrastructure to enable the described processing activities
- Processing of contact details for verification, clarification, traceability, and communication purposes related to the data, including, where necessary, limited sharing with third parties in accordance with the PEH Data Platform Terms and Conditions.

Further details regarding the use, sharing, or publication of aggregated data, metadata, and other outputs are governed by the PEH Data Platform Terms and Conditions.

Appendix 2: Instructions regarding the Processing of Personal Data

As the Agreement includes the more general provisions, it is important for the Controller to explicitly specify its instructions regarding the processing by the Processor. These instructions may concern inter alia the following:

- 1) The Controller instructs the Processor to:
 - a. Process single measurement data within the PEH Data Platform environment
 - b. Not disclose single measurement data to any third party, unless:
 - i. required to do so by Union or Member State law, or
 - ii. explicitly instructed or authorized by the Controller.In any such case, the Processor shall inform the Controller prior to the disclosure, unless legally prohibited.
 - c. Apply validation, harmonization, and enrichment procedures as implemented in the platform
 - d. Generate aggregated data (summary statistics), metadata, and other defined outputs, and make these available in accordance with the PEH Data Platform Terms and Conditions
 - e. Process contact details strictly for verification, clarification, and communication purposes related to the data, in accordance with Appendix 1 and the PEH Data Platform Terms and Conditions

- 2) The use of subcontractors: In case a Processor engages another sub-processor for carrying out specific processing activities on behalf of the Controller, the same data protection obligations as set out in the Agreement between the controller and the processor shall be imposed on that other sub-processor by way of a contract or other legal act under Union or Member State law, in particular providing sufficient guarantees to implement appropriate technical and organizational measures in such a manner that the processing will meet the requirements of this GDPR. Where that other sub-processor fails to fulfil its data protection obligations, the initial Processor shall remain fully liable to the Controller for the performance of that other sub-processor's obligations.

In other words the instructions may include that the same obligations as set out in this Agreement between the Controller and the Processor shall be imposed on the sub-processor.

- 3) Instructions regarding confidentiality: the Controller could include a provision which states that the employees of the Processor should among others have signed a confidentiality clause. There should be internal policies with clear instructions for all those that process the Personal Data. These instructions may also include the more technical side and may refer to the security measures in annex 3.

- 4) Security of processing: refer to annex 3 for specific technical and organizational measures that must be taken to ensure the security of the Processing.

The Controller is exclusively responsible for overall compliance with the DPA, however it can still contract out certain tasks related to this to its data processor. For example when a Controller receives a request to access data from a data subject, the Controller can either require the Processor to provide it with the requested data so that the Controller can deal with the request itself, or give instructions to the Processor so that the Processor can deal with the request on behalf of the Controller. This second option is only feasible if it is a routine subject access request. The Controller shall specify to the Processor how to handle the request, for example by stipulating if there are any categories of information that it should withhold.

The Controller should specify the required assistance it expects from the Processor for the fulfilment of the Controller's obligation to respond to requests for exercising the data subject's rights. How should the Controller help the Processor?

Appendix 3: Security of Processing

Summary of Technical & Organizational Measures (TOM)

1.1 Information Security Policy

VITO has an Information Security Policy to enable the principles and organisation of information security at VITO. This contributes to the strategic objective of optimally safeguarding information security and strengthening our cyber resilience.

The VITO Information Security Policy:

- Is approved by VITO management, published and communicated to all employees and relevant stakeholders.
- Is systematically reviewed, or if significant changes occur to ensure its continuing suitability, adequacy, and effectiveness.
- Contains a set of domain specific policies addressing information & cyber-security.

1.2 Organization of Information Security

In accordance with the VITO Information Security Policy, all information security responsibilities are defined and allocated (ISO, DPO, decision-making structures, etc.)

In addition to the overall governance related to privacy and cybersecurity, VITO:

- Has domain specific policies and operational procedures for addressing information security risks in a structured manner.
- Has a process for conducting Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) where required.
- Has requirements on implementing privacy and security by design.
- Has a Incident-response-procedure stipulating the appropriate contacts with relevant authorities and external parties, concerning information security incidents (NIS2), and data breaches (GDPR). See 1.10 below.
- Is formally registered as an 'Essential Entity' under the Centre for Cybersecurity Belgium by adhering to the CyberFundamentals framework, in alignment with the NIS2 directive requirements in Belgium.
- Maintains appropriate contacts with special interest groups or other specialists, security forums and professional associations. The goals of such contacts are, among others, staying up-to-date, developing best practices, getting informed quickly when new threats arrive, getting access to specialized services and exchanging information and experiences.

1.3 Human Resource Security

In respect to Human Resource security, the focus lies on ensuring that all personnel understand and fulfill their information security responsibilities.

Therefore VITO :

- Has contractual agreements with employees and contractors that state the responsibilities for information security for both parties. The employee contract stipulates how to handle confidential information. Furthermore, standard clauses are used (e.g. for Ph.D. students) as well as data processing agreements and NDA's (in case of external employees related to sub-processors).
- Makes all employees of VITO and relevant contractors aware of the risks and the importance of information security. On a regular basis, employees receive appropriate awareness education regarding information security, including phishing-simulations, to improve awareness and correct actions.
- Has a formal and communicated disciplinary process in place to take action against employees who have, willingly or unwillingly, committed an information security breach.

- Has information security responsibilities and duties in place that remain valid after termination or a change of employment. NDA's are defined, made enforceable, and communicated to the employee or contractor.

1.4 Asset Management

In regard to asset management, the focus is on identifying, classifying, and protecting information assets to ensure their appropriate handling throughout their lifecycle.

In response, VITO:

- Maintains an inventory of assets associated with information processing in a CMDB (Configuration management database).
- Assigns to each asset in the CMDB a designated owner, responsible for governance and operational integrity.
- Requires that asset owners adhere to an 'Acceptable Use Policy', which is being established to outline the rules for asset usage throughout its lifecycle. This includes clear instructions on data storage, secure transfer, proper disposal, and other handling procedures.
- Classifies an asset based on the sensitivity level of the data it processes, in accordance with the organization's Data Classification Policy. This classification influences the required security controls and compliance obligations.⁷
- Reviews the asset management practices periodically to ensure they remain aligned with applicable regulatory requirements and are consistent with the principles outlined in the VITO Information Security Policy.

1.5 Access control

Through access control mechanisms, VITO ensures that access to information and systems is restricted to authorized individuals based on defined roles, responsibilities, and the principle of least privilege and need to know.

Accordingly, VITO:

- Has defined and implemented a comprehensive password policy. It governs requirements for password settings, including strength (complexity), change (rotation) and attack prevention, across various account types, including administrative, service, and user accounts.
- Has defined and implemented an access control policy, aligned with both functional business needs and information security requirements. It applies conditional access policies based on strong authentication mechanisms, including two-factor authentication (e.g. Authenticator apps, Biometrics, client certificates on managed laptops,...) for remote network access, and privileged accounts. These measures are actively maintained and further expanded to external facing assets.
- Enforces network authentication across all VITO networks—wired and wireless—ensuring that all activities are both authenticated and authorized. VLAN access is managed via a NAC tool.
- Has formal procedures in place for user onboarding and offboarding, enabling the appropriate assignment and deactivation of access rights. These processes are initiated via HR workflows and are largely executed through automated workflows.

1.6 Physical and Environmental Security

On behalf of physical security, VITO focusses on protecting facilities, equipment, and information from unauthorized physical access, damage, or disruption.

To mitigate these threats, VITO:

- Has defined a physical security policy and implemented a comprehensive set of physical security controls.

- Uses a physical security perimeter to protect areas that contain either sensitive or critical information and information processing facilities.
 - Protects secure zones with access controls to restrict entry to authorized personnel only and strictly supervises access to the datacenters. (e.g. camera surveillance, badge control to track access)
 - Has protective measures in place against natural disasters, malicious threats, and accidental damage.
 - Has shielded critical equipment from power outages and utility disruptions.
 - Has established and enforced procedures for operating within secure areas.
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- Physically protects data-carrying power and telecom cables against interception, interference, and manages VLAN access via a NAC tool.
 - Has procedures in place to ensure sensitive data is securely erased or overwritten before disposal or reuse of VITO devices with storage media.
 - Configures critical infrastructure components redundantly to ensure continuity in case of equipment failure.

1.7 Operations Security

Through operational security practices, VITO aims to ensure the secure and resilient management of information processing facilities, systems, and supporting infrastructure.

Therefore VITO :

- Monitors and optimizes system resource usage continuously, supported by capacity forecasting to maintain performance.
- Configures critical components in high-availability mode to ensure resilience in the event of asset failure.
- Applies a layered security approach to reduce the risk of malware and cyberattacks, including: (Web Application) Firewalls
- Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (IDPS)
- Endpoint protection and encryption
- Ransomware protection for data storage
- Network access control
- Automated isolation of compromised endpoints or users
- Security event monitoring and alerting
- Has implemented Backup and restore procedures, ensuring regular creation and testing of backups for data, software, and system images, in line with the backup policy.
- Maintains a patch management process to deploy critical security updates in a timely manner, and applies compensating controls such as network isolation, system hardening, or virtual patching when patching is not feasible.
- Supports vulnerability management through automated scanning tools.
- Secures email communication using multiple protective measures, including authentication protocols (SPF, DKIM, DMARC), phishing filters, safe link protection, and automated scanning of attachments and URLs.
- Applies hardened standard images to system configurations, aligning with industry-recognized security standards.

1.8 Security of the Communication

To safeguard the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information exchanged across internal and external networks, VITO enforces strong communication security measures.

In response, VITO:

- Secures all networks to prevent unauthorized access and ensure safe data transmission.
- Implements network segregation through VLANs, ensuring that critical systems requiring elevated protection are isolated from less sensitive segments.
- Includes confidentiality clauses in contracts involving third-party data exchange, such as NDAs and data processing agreements, in alignment with GDPR requirements.

1.9 System Acquisition, Development, Maintenance & Third party risk

To ensure that information security and privacy requirements are embedded throughout the system lifecycle and services — from planning to development, implementation and ongoing support — VITO applies structured practices that also address third-party risk.

To embed this, VITO:

- Incorporates information security requirements into specifications for new systems and enhancements to existing ones.
- Protects application services that transmit data over public networks against fraud, unauthorized access, and data modification by using encrypted protocols such as HTTPS and SFTP where possible.
- Reviews and tests business-critical applications when operating platforms are changed, ensuring continuity and security are not compromised.
- Applies a controlled SCRUM process to implement software modifications based on business requests.
- Defines and documents information security requirements for suppliers who access organizational assets. This is done systematically for data processors under GDPR, and as needed for other suppliers.
- Conducts regular service review meetings with key suppliers to monitor performance and address security expectations.
- Ensures that third-party engagements are governed by appropriate contractual safeguards, including confidentiality clauses, NDAs, and data processing agreements where applicable.

1.10 Incident Management

To minimize the impact of security events and foster continuous improvement, VITO ensures that incidents are promptly identified, reported, assessed, and resolved through a structured incident management process.

Therefore, VITO:

- Maintains an Incident Response Plan that is regularly reviewed and updated to remain effective and aligned with evolving threats.
- Applies formal criteria to classify incidents as data breaches or significant security incidents, in accordance with the GDPR and/or NIS2 regulation.
- Follows a documented procedure for responding to and reporting incidents or data breaches, ensuring that responsibilities and actions are clearly defined to enable a swift, structured, and effective response. This includes timely communication with management, affected data subjects, the Data Protection Authority (DPA), the National CERT, in line with applicable legal and regulatory requirements.